
A Comparative Study between Online and Traditional Counseling for Students with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD): School Psychologists Perspective in the Obsequies of Pandemic COVID-19

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Abstract

Counseling is essential in the current situation of pandemic COVID-19 for special needs children. Many previous researchers discuss the therapy and treatment use during counseling and investigate teachers' role during counseling, but little much knows about online counseling and methods. This study shows the comparison between online and traditional counseling for students with ADHD. A qualitative research design was used in this study, while the nature of the study was phenomenological. In this study, the interview guide based on Skinner's reinforcement theory. The study's findings revealed that reinforcement techniques for ADHD children use in both traditional and online counseling. Traditional counseling is better than online counseling. Face to face counseling shows early improvement as compare to online counseling. School psychologists face more problems during traditional counseling. Future implications and ways are discussed.

Keywords: School Psychologists, ADHD Students, online counseling, Traditional counseling

Introduction

The Covid-19 pandemic speaks to a specific worldwide health emergency (Chen et al., 2020). One of the significant issues and crises show in the special education sector. Due to COVID-19 see the many severe health issues, financial crisis, economic effects but major crises show in the education sector internationally in which Pakistan also included. Virus COVID-19 second wave spread fast as compare to the first wave all over the world. Recently till January 20, the number of affected patients of COVID-19 is 524,783. It creates a destructive impact on education and changes the education system traditional way of online education system. Pakistan's government applied lockdown many times in educational institutes also globally; almost all

universities, schools, and colleges remain off. Lockdown or local isolate is executed in the education sector to diminish and lessen the Covid plague. (Abdullah, 2020) for next generations and future students. In fact in reality base lockdown create a negative effect on education and the learning process (Yanti et al., 2020). Online learning helps to control the spread of COVID-19 and maintain social distancing. Students need direction and counseling services with the utilization of innovation during the Covid-19 pandemic. Online coordinated effort and innovative status affect the accomplishment of students. Direction and counseling services are critically required for students at any school, special education center, college, and university because students experience different issues. The types of issues experienced by students are emotional well-being issues, falsehood issues, instructive issues, and adapting system issues (Pragholapati, 2020). Skinner's theory has been executed in educational systems in an assortment of ways. Teachers looking to execute reinforcement system in their classroom should utilize systems, for example, a "token economy" to remunerate learners quickly for practices that they are reinforcing. Psychologists deal individually with all age groups, families, and institutions. Psychologists deal the emotional, social, school, and physical health problems, life stresses, and other severe issues. They collaborate with teachers, administrators, and other schools and develop strategies for general issues. School psychologists address the child's academic and developmental problems. School psychologists assist and overcome the specific type of disability. They develop strategies to address the behavioral issues with the help of a teacher and school administrator. School psychologists prepare IEP for students (Armour, Müllerová, & Elhai, 2016). Behavior therapists mostly adapt Skinner's theory to modify and change the behavior of children in a classroom. Numerous children's experience challenges sitting as yet, focusing on tasks, and embarrass their behavior. These qualities are practically natural for child development. However, if these behaviors start to influence academic, friends, and family connections, Diagnose of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) might be assured (DuPaul and Stoner, 2003). Much literature on ADHD focuses on the factors, symptoms, causes, treatment, and medication-related to this disorder.

However, numerous misconceptions about ADHD and their counseling through school psychologists still exist, these misconceptions directly affect the school staff, environment, parents, and individual with ADHD (Flanigan, 2016). In Pakistan, ADHD has been found around 2.49%. If we compare children with and without ADHD, find children with more injuries (59% vs. 49%). Children with ADHD diagnosing rate increase a common of 3% per the year 1997 to 2006 and common increase 5% per the year 2003 to 2011. Boys who diagnose with ADHD rate are 13.2% and girl's rate is 5.6% (Mohamed and Sciences, 2016).

Hupp, Reitman, & Jewell (2008) discuss Skinner's theory of operant behavior additionally represents decreases in the quality of conduct. Specifically, operant conditioning includes retaining the introduction of results keeping up given conduct, though negative reinforcement includes lessening the recurrence of conduct by the evacuation of an outcome following the presentation of a behavior. Positive reinforcement includes debilitating conduct by including over stimulate unforeseen exhibition of conduct. Skinner incorporates precursor sin his examinations of fortification possibilities and explicitly concentrating on forerunner improvements (e.g., separate upgrades) that control social reactions on account of a background marked by support within the sight of those boosts. First contemplated widely by Skinner (1938) and Ferster and Skinner (1957) Skinner's theory of operant behavior additionally

represents decreases in the quality of conduct. Specifically operant conditioning includes retaining the introduction of results keeping up a given conduct, though negative reinforcement includes lessening the recurrence of conduct by the evacuation of an outcome following the presentation of a behavior. Positive reinforcement includes debilitating conduct by including over stimulate unforeseen the exhibition of a conduct. Skinner incorporates precursor sin his examinations of fortification possibilities and explicitly concentrating on forerunner improvements (e.g., separate upgrades) that control social reactions on account of a background marked by support within the sight of those boosts. First contemplated widely by Skinner (1938) and Ferster and Skinner (1957) support is characterized as the procedure wherein the consequence of conduct reinforces the future likelihood of the conduct.

School Psychologists can give online counseling during the Covid-19 pandemic. Individual counseling as help school teachers can give individual counseling service during the Covid-19 pandemic. They were advising as help by specialists to people who need to take care of ecological issues. School psychologists as professionals for helping students. School psychologists improving the mental condition of students and guardians in reducing elevated levels of pressure, tension, gloom, and other mental conditions through web-based directing, conveyance of illness avoidance pamphlets, sites, YouTube instructional exercise recordings, recordings, short movies, online conversations through WhatsApp gatherings, and different methods (Ifdil, Fadli, Suranata, Zola, & Ardi, 2020).

School psychologists had appreciably better information of ADHD than teachers and their big schooling and schooling associated with ADHD. School psychologists are relatively skilled in all of these areas, making them priceless within the assessment and capacity diagnosis of ADHD (Flanigan, 2016). Recently on any research conducted on special needs children counselling in Pakistan. ADHD students mostly need various therapies and medication as an intervention, but no proper therapies and medication are provided to them in particular educational institutions. In government sector counselling is not gave on a regular base. The problem is that school psychologists have no command of how to use technology during online counselling. They don't know about the effectiveness of counselling through online counselling. Online learning is very beneficial in a condition of COVID-19. It helps special needs children to improve their lives and skills at home. This study was performed to compare traditional online counselling methods to children with ADHD and discover it too alliance between psychologists feedback about the preferred method of teaching and their respective genders.

This present study explores school psychologists' diverse experiences during online and traditional counselling to students with ADHD. This study aims to know which learning mode is best for ADHD students side by side with other special needs children to provide better health care to children. To highlight school psychologists choose from different cities of Pakistan where school psychologists deal with ADHD children and provide online counselling session during pandemic COVID-19 first wave and second wave. This study explores which mode of counselling is more effective for ADHD children and investigates the techniques that school psychologists use in online and traditional counselling. This study developed some question about differentiating traditional and online counselling during COVID-19.

1- What are the school psychologists knowledge about online and traditional counselling?

2- Which various techniques school psychologists use during online and traditional counselling?

3- What is the effectiveness of online and traditional counselling during pandemic COVID-19?

4- What are the experiences of school psychologists during online and traditional counselling?

Research Method

The research opted for qualitative research design according to the need of the research because research needs more in-depth and detailed information about reinforcement techniques used during counseling traditional and online sessions for ADHD students. Only through qualitative research get a detailed interview and collect overall information about the use of reinforcement techniques during counseling. The researchers choose the nature of the basic qualitative research design for this study.

The population of this study was entire school psychologists working in special education public and private centers of districts Lahore, Hafiz Abad, Kamonki, and Gujranwala. Some special centers enrolled ADHD students in their centers and school psychologists give counseling sessions. Twenty school psychologists choose from Pakistan different cities (Lahore, Kamonki, Hafizabad, and Gujranwala). A purposive sampling technique was used for this research. Only the school psychologists who are working as a psychologist in a special education institution included in this study. School psychologists working with Autism, ADHD, and Learning disability students and give almost 15 sessions to Autism, ADHD, and Learning disability students. All school psychologists have done their degree in clinical psychology, applied behavior analysis or diploma in a behavior therapist included in this study. All the school psychologists have a minimum of three years' experience of counseling in special centers or a private center. The data was collected from November 2020 to December 2020. Prior approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee.

Instrument

Researchers developed the interview guide with the help of a literature review and Skinner's reinforcement theory (Skinner, 1965). Recent studies and published articles related to this topic helps to develop an interview guide. A semi-structured interview guide was developed to know about the difference between the traditional and online way of counseling use school psychologists for children with ADHD.

Data Collection Method

Researchers collect the list of special centers and collect data through a semi-structured interview. Researchers briefly describe the aim of the study to participants before starting the interview. The validity of the interview guide was to make sure from the field experts and supervisors. All the experts gave positive feedback and make some changes to it. After the validation, the data collection process was started but a pilot study was carried out by 3 school psychologists, after taking consent from these participants. The pilot study of the study identifies the clarity of questions related to the study. Students and the newly hire psychologists were excluded from this study. Based on the results of the pilot study, it is necessary to question mark was modified.

Data Analysis

The above image show during online counseling moves around three persons. It's also called the triangle way of counseling. School psychologists, child, and parents involved in online counseling. SP indirectly takes a part in online counseling. Another diagram show face to face counseling. In which only two persons were directly involved. Only school psychologists and child take a part in counseling.

Table 3

Table 3 shows the SP answers difference about themes. SP face more challenges during face to face counseling. Counseling is effective in both ways

of counseling. SP follow the counseling techniques strictly in a face to face counseling. SP experience during face to face counseling is much better as compare to online counseling. Long term and short term goals achieve timely during face to face counseling.

Traditional Way of Counseling	Online Way of Counseling
Face to face	No interaction with a child
Working on Child weak areas	3 persons include during counseling
Assessment update on a monthly bases	Use different Apps Zoom, WhatsApp video call, Hangout or Messenger, Google Classroom for upload goal plans
Working on different domain	Assessment is not doing in a monthly bases
Working under the supervision of Head	Naturalistic way of teaching use
Use specific technique according to the child need	Guide parents during call how to handle their child
Work start before discussing all aspects and get training	Goals update by psychologists and share with parents
Weekly group counseling held	No proper prompt level use during session
Proper reinforcement schedule use for a child	Focus on a child each behavior
Working on all behaviors of a child side by side	Session miss because of light issue or some family issue
Focus on peer interaction	No proper goals run
Use proper Reinforcement technique for decreasing child inappropriate behavior and to decrease child require behavior	Supervisor cannot supervise all children at a time
Day to Day activities decide after pre assessment and observing child	Parents exhaust many times
After mastered goals new goals decide with the help of lead	No proper reinforcement schedule follow

Results of the Study:

Theme

Knowledge about Different Way of Counseling

Responses

Most of the participants have complete knowledge about how to deliver a session at the center. They know what ADHD is and how to handle a child at the center. They use Conner's rating scale to diagnose ADHD children. They highlight that this scale includes the teachers rating scale and parents rating scale. They report parents rating scale has four options that are closely related to the child's parents. Some participants have complete command about online therapy or session. They stated that online session means to guide parents on how to handle their child at home during pandemic or verse situation. Through online sessions parents also side by

side train and have the grip to manage child aggressive behaviors. Some participants thought that the traditional way of counseling is better as compare to online learning because at the center they build different skills, self-esteem in a child. During the online session, they only depend on parents and most of the time parents are not willing to do this. Child regress and never able to do something. According to participants they treat the child directly and know the reason for the behavior but parents during online sessions never understand the situation and reinforce the child negatively. Few participants prefer online counseling they proposed that this is beneficial for parents because it's not a two-way session. Three persons are involved in it and the child mostly attaches with the parents and shows better performance as compared to at the center.

Counseling Techniques use during Session

Most all participants use reinforcement techniques in both traditional and online way of counseling. Most of the participants use a structured way of counseling at a center in which the child came at the center sit on the chair and follow the command sofa psychologists. They elaborate that reinforcement techniques include giving rewards like candies or biscuits, clapping, or appreciating him/her. They use reinforcement techniques also when the child is sitting without creating any disturbance. They report that they have a session of about 15- 25 minutes. They take 2 to 3 counseling sessions a week for ADHD children. They give reinforcement immediately increases the attention span of the child and improves sitting behavior that is very helpful to convey the message in the next session easily. They make a weekly chart in which they give stars to the children for a positive response. They emphasize that this chart clearly explains the reward list to the children which they receive after the positive feedback. They always appreciate the children by given techniques. In this way, they do some activities like jumping, swimming, racing, and art. During the online session, they use the Naturalistic way of teaching in which a non-structured way of teaching follows. Some participants prefer the naturalistic way of teaching because children explore many things in a natural environment. A child shows the excitement and takes an interest to learn something new. On the other hand, few participants stated that both ways of teaching are good if side by side run. According to the demand of a child way to teaching modify and after the child able to do something changes the strategy. According to the most participants counseling technique properly follow at the center. Parents never follow the proper way of reinforcement technique. They give too much reinforcement in negative behavior in which the child regresses. They have not enough knowledge about professional things. Some participants suggested that during online sessions parents follow all strategies and techniques. Some time parents explore a new way of teaching and take an interest that shows a big improvement in a child. Some participants stated that at the center they use play therapy and behavior modification techniques to convey a message during counseling sessions to the ADHD children. They use to start with the easy steps then take difficult steps to change the behavior of the child. They state that in play therapy, they choose different activities according to the child e.g. games, jumping, racing, puzzles, blocks, etc. They suggest that in behavior therapy they ensure to include parents in this therapy. They think play therapy helps to convey message with the help of some indoor and outdoor activities. .

Experiences of Psychologists	of	School	<p>Most of the participants state that they feel difficulty to handle ADHD children during online session. According to them during online session they never face challenges as such because physically child is not present. Parents handle child they only guide them but at the end many other behaviors and aggression came in a child. During online parents never listen therapist and put own command to the child. Some participants discussed that they feel difficulty during traditional way of counseling. They remark that every child has a different symptoms and level. They increase their temperament to handle these children. They said that severe children give very tough time during counseling. They describe that children have too much energy and hyperactivity so reduce all these things need an extra time, plan and energy. They report that most of the time parents fade up with all these things and cutoff the counseling sessions. They increase their stamina and patience to deal ADHD children. They state that ADHD children cannot sit at one place. They always stand behind the child. They report that when parents do not attend the session they feel fatigue and burden during sessions. They exhaust energy to run behind the child that has also very difficult. They try their best for the improvement in the child with the help of medication. They emphasize that through individual counseling psychologists manage all behaviors problems of a child, e.g., sitting, eating, bathing, jumping, swimming, and running etc. They suggest that children can never survive in group counseling with these problems. They make a chart for every child and discuss all points and routine of a child in it. Few participants state that they enjoy the sessions with ADHD children. Their experiences were beautiful because they believe they know all things about ADHD. They see the improvement and changing in the child. They suggest that if parents cannot support or cooperative even they enjoy work and handle the child. They manage the children in a proper way because they think in beginning the child does not listen to them but they realize child understand all things and speech. They never dominate the children during counseling. They communicate with the children and enjoy the communication because children pick their point quickly and give response.</p>
Effectiveness of Traditional and Online Counseling			<p>The entire participants report that counseling is 100% effective for ADHD children. They state that counseling helps ADHD children to change their behavior and hyperactivity. They suggest that ADHD requires constant supervision and persistent professional coaching. They use different strategies like therapies, guidance, play therapy, reinforcement, behavior therapy which helps psychologists to understand the children behavior in problematic situation. They propose that through counseling parents also feel relaxed about their children. They emphasize that ADHD children need two things: The sense that they're successful, both socially and academically, and unconditional love from their parents, if either is missing, a child will have a hard time developing a sense of self-esteem. They suggest that counseling develops all these things and skills in a children and parents. They suggest that counseling is effective in both ways. They never left the child without guidance. Most of the participants state that they plan the day to day activities for every ADHD child. They make a plan for every week at the start of the every week. In this plan, they use stationary, coloring books, cards, charts, jumping, football, cricket, puzzles, blocks, toys, tricks, reinforcement, worksheet, sports, and all indoor, outdoor activities and attention sustaining activities. In the plan, they mention all week's activities. They suggest that IEP has also helpful</p>

for them to make day to day activity plan. They discuss that in IEP mention child all week points and issues then child activities arrange according to their points. They report that children severity level is also important to make a plan. Sometimes, they modify or change the activity plan if the child has hyper or sad in today's session then they choose another activity and do it with the child. Few participants state that they do not make day to day activity plan. They report that ADHD child activity plan decide for a twice a day in a week. They only make a plan of individual sessions or a group session. They emphasize that they make an activity plan how to engage the child twice in a week. They never made an all-week plan of activity only a two-day activity plan made by psychologist. They state that psychologist use activities in a counseling sessions and performed with the child. They report that play and behavior therapy have best for design activities. They think music therapy also adds in activities. They state that when the children come to school and attend sessions they feel anxiety. They emphasize that counseling release their anxiety and depression. They underscore that counseling is effective both for children and adults at any level like mild, moderate, severe and profound. Online counseling is effective when no option left.

Discussion

School psychologist's role is very influential to change the behavior and mind of ADHD children. The students who are attention deficit, school counselors play essential role of screening for ADHD (Castelnau et al, 2017). Psychologists not only motivate or guide the children during counseling. Therapists only suggest therapies during session. No new therapy, technique or strategies they apply during counseling of ADHD children. These results are consistent with a research conducted by (Shabanpour, Mohammadyfar, TalePesand, and Rezaei, 2017). Skinner behavior operant learning theory was used to strengthen the behavior in different ways. Reinforcement technique helps change the behavior in a variety of ways and through learning process. This technique include Punishment (weakens behavior), behavior modification therapies, neutral and positive reinforces (Gordan & Krishanan, 2014). Token economy also include with person or child target behavior changes with the help of different tokens like fake money, clue cards etc. This study also helps to control the human self-control, behaviors and emotions. Psychologists use the rules of the behaviorists and follow the principals of the theory which discuss in different theory of behaviorists during treatment of the children. School counselors have no time to read latest researchers and adapt innovative methods of counseling for ADHD students. In Pakistan, school psychologists are hiring not for a specific disorder. One psychologist gives counseling sessions to all disability children, who have the degree of masters in special education also include in psychologists. No specific age limit and qualification held for the counselors.

School counselors develop different skills in ADHD children through counseling. They improve academic, social, daily living skills of ADHD children but if the child has a mild level disability. Severe children cannot develop all these skills because counselor has not enough train and knowledge about this. School counselors used old pattern in which specific and limited skills improved and better in children. No vocational or technical skill develops in ADHD children for better and secure future.

Results of the study shows that traditional way of counseling in which face to face session provide better as compare to online counseling. In the online session the children regress and then have to start again from level one. Many school psychologists agreed that in face to face counseling improvement show in a child as compare to online counseling. This study also explore that online counseling help during pandemic or any critical situation in which children stuck on same level as well as the children have interaction with the parents. with the help of online learning parents know the importance of counseling and hard work of therapist do.

School psychologists choose different ways and methods in online counseling to change the behavior of the children. They choose reinforcement techniques, token economy, and play therapy, outdoor and indoor activities. School counselors cannot contact with psychiatrist at the start of the counseling because ADHD children have a medically problem. School psychologists use medication only for the child sleeps well and attend counseling sessions in a fresh mood. In face to face counseling, School psychologists divided a counseling session into a different long term and short term goals. If a child cannot perform in a one goal they change the goal after three trials.

Reinforcement technique helps to develop different socialization and behavior changes in children. Continuing counseling and short term counseling also call cognitive therapy or talk therapy give children with ADHD with a secure, strategies for ADHD (low, 2019).

Reinforcement technique usually properly used in face to face counseling in which they give different rewards like appreciate, clapping, positive reinforced, social reinforcement, child preference item or toy and they chose different activities according to children interest. It helps to develop different domains skills like academic, receptive language, identification, concept of give, find, touch, dressing, grooming, social and cognition in a child. In most School psychologists didn't know about difference between reinforcement technique and therapy. In Government sector of Pakistan they didn't give parents concealing to ADHD students even they are not allowed to meet with sp. School psychologists give indirect concealing to parents when they come to school (Boucher's, pamphlets). School psychologists teach the class teachers of ADHD students to tell parents how to treat their child at home. School counselors prefer both individual and group parents concealing but they don't have clear concept about individual and group concealing. In other countries School counselors start their concealing with parents, Guide then and make a chart how to deal with childe according to different situations. Almost in these cases mother are more hyper and aggressive then ADHD child. According to School counselors if ADHD child is behaving rudely and hyper, Mother behave more hyper and shout on child.

Online way of counseling is easy as compare to face to face because through online SP are not directly connected to the child. They only guide parents and make plan for a child. SP face more challenges during face to face counseling. According to them at centre they face more problems like parents ignorance, lack of family interaction, child aggressive behavior modification. They apply techniques to overcome these problems.

The study revealed that traditional counseling is much better as compare to online counseling. Online counseling is need for critical situation of pandemic because special needs children need continuously assistance. If therapy or session stop they regress and all undesirable behaviors occurs. Through online counseling its provide another way for parents how to manage their child behaviors and skills at home. On the other hand it is beneficial to build interaction an repo building with child and parents. parents take interest in child program and work. They look motivate about positivity and there is a hope within the parents that we can fix our children too. Parents not only rely on the centres but motivate them. Traditional counseling helpful for joins who left their child at centre for few hours.

In Pakistan the old tradition, (dam, darood) is very popular. Parents suggest peer group and believe in spiritual prayers. ADHD children mostly find in shrines. Once assistant professor of a special education department go to some child, his child diagnose with ADHD. After dam he said now my child is better. Government introduces 15 seats in a year for school psychologists. Systematic environment is compulsory because in Pakistan joint family system is very common. In which if the child is with ADHD they become more aggressive or hyper. Mostly parents or siblings slap on face and child become hyper.

Conclusion

Pilot study results indicate that there is no difference between traditional and online counseling of students with ADHD. However, the study participant's results show a huge difference between traditional and online counseling. After

analyzing the study's conclusion, the investigator had concluded that almost 90% of school psychologists use reinforcement techniques in both traditional and online counseling. School psychologists develop limited skills during online counseling in ADHD children. In rare cases, ADHD children, mostly in special schools, shifted into hospitals. During online counseling, most parents do not know the counselors. Counseling is the better solution to change the ADHD child's behavior. Counseling is very effective for ADHD students because counseling has no side effects like medication. A combination of both things counseling and medication shows better results and improvement in a child. It shows counseling is more effective than medication. ADHD students generate more neuron chemicals; parents are unaware of this. Hospital has a separate department of child psychiatry. In which all counselors are very trained, experienced and deal with ADHD children properly. If the student is very hyper or in severe condition, the school is referred to the hospital. Psychologists give counseling sessions with medication. ADHD requires constant supervision and persistent professional coaching. Reinforcement techniques psychologists used and followed the principles of Thorndike and Pavlov theories. A reinforcement technique has different steps and rules.

The study revealed that the traditional way of counseling is more effective and better than online counseling. School counselors choose this technique through short term and long term goals. Apply all reinforcement techniques to run all goals in a session. This technique helps change a child's behavior socially, eye contact, seat, aggression, grab things, and name response in different activities.

The study concluded that counseling is very important for ADHD students in both ways, but the traditional counseling method shows more benefits and results. Online counseling sometimes increases negative behaviors in the child. Face to face counseling always decreases the negative behaviors of a child. Sp always faces more problems in the face to face counseling as compare to online counseling because face to face counseling includes two persons. Online is an indirect way of counseling and includes three persons.

Limitation

There is a limit to this research. The study was limited in that it was conducted with only twenty school psychologists who take online counseling sessions during pandemic-19 first wave and second wave. It was also conducted during the second wave of pandemic COVID-19 lockdown, which limited the sample size and interaction. These all factors help to reduce the generalizability of the results.

Recommendations

In support of the study's findings and conclusion, the below recommendations suggest that the government should hire some experts and experienced trainers in the selection committee of counselors. All the school psychologists must have a degree of MSc clinical psychology or MSc in psychology and an advanced diploma in clinical psychology. Government and private sector institutions should collaborate and facilitate new therapies and school counselors' techniques to smoothly take online sessions. The government should hold awareness workshops and seminars for parents on how to manage their child at home. **Recommendation for Future Research**

School psychologists reported that the traditional way of counseling is much better as compare to online counseling. They face more challenges during traditional counseling, not in online sessions. Future researchers need to address the gaps that exist in online counseling. Also, explore the ways which create more problems in the face to face counseling. Online counseling is not consistent with traditional counseling. It is a more important factor to explore in the future.

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